

EVALUATING THE JOB SATISFACTION OF HIGH SCHOOL TEACHERS AMID THE HEALTH CRISIS IN ORMOC CITY, LEYTE, PHILIPPINES

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This study aimed to elucidate the job satisfaction level and capture its governing factors among high school teachers in Ormoc City, Leyte, Philippines. In selecting the participants, a simple random sampling was applied to three chosen high schools in Ormoc City, and primary data were gathered from them. Some descriptive statistics were computed to describe the data and the Chi-square test for association was employed to determine the relationship between any two variables. Results of the calculation depicted that, on average, teachers are "satisfied" with their jobs despite the challenges of modular distance education amid the lockdown brought on by the health crisis. The Chi-square test has revealed that if the highest educational attainment is a bachelor's degree, conducive workplace assignment, and lower job categorization are determinants of work satisfaction among high school teachers during modular distance education. This implies that teachers with minimal and doable workloads are more satisfied in their jobs during the new normal. In addition, if the teachers are comfortable in their workplace, they are motivated to work despite the difficulties they have encountered during the pandemic. Hence, the study suggests that school leaders must adjust to lessening the workload of teachers to avoid stress and burnout.

Keywords: Secondary teachers, job satisfaction, causal determinants, chi-square test

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1. INTRODUCTION

Being a teacher is not an easy undertaking especially when they are facing some challenges beyond their control. During the time of COVID-19 pandemic, schools were shut down and shifted immediately to modular distance learning or online learning (Casinillo et al., 2022; Castroverde & Acala, 2021; Talimodao & Madrigal, 2021). During that scenario, both students and teachers encountered several unprecedented obstacles and limitations that adversely affected their teaching-learning process (Chen et al., 2020; Islam et al., 2020; Pressley & Ha, 2021). Teachers dealt with printing ready-made module/lecture guides and learning tasks and distributing them to their students without a proper discussion (Talimodao & Madrigal, 2021). After ample time, they have it collected for checking the students' output. This process is routine until the school year ends. In fact, teachers are experiencing job burnout and stress because of their exhausting work and boring situations (Sokal et al., 2020). On the face of it, teachers' well-being is negatively affected which causes them to have low levels of job satisfaction. According to Dicke et al. (2020), teachers' job satisfaction is closely related to the performance of students. However, teachers cannot monitor the student's academic achievement and progress due to barriers amid the health protocols. Hence, a low level of job satisfaction for teachers is depicted during the pandemic (Chitra, 2020).

During the time of the health crisis, teachers did not just focus on their students' learning but they were also bothered with their health as well as their family's safety. In fact, the health and safety of every individual during the pandemic were of the utmost concern (Hashim et al., 2020). In this regard, they were working as an educator while their mind was thinking of other concern with their family's survival which caused them depression (Auger & Formentin, 2021). Moreover, the study by Hashim et al. (2020) stressed that teachers' job satisfaction during the pandemic was diminishing which resulted in low well-being due to stressful and draining paperwork in distance education. It is worth noting that the performance of teachers and as well as the motivation rely on their job satisfaction (Balasundran et al., 2021). Apparently, it is vital to do research on how to increase teachers' job satisfaction by investigating the determinants affecting it. In that case, one can find a remedy to positively increase the job satisfaction level of high school teachers and to somehow improve the quality of education despite the obstacles of the pandemic. In fact, Ertürk (2022) has emphasized that job satisfaction can improve teachers' quality and minimize turnover intentions, especially in the challenging distance learning setup. Moreover, Iwu et al. (2018) stated that a

quality education can be achieved by understanding the determinants of teachers' job satisfaction and well-being.

The study about job satisfaction is not new in the body of literature, however, investigating high school teachers' job satisfaction and predicting its determinants during the new normal is a bit limited in the Philippine setting. In fact, no research study has been conducted in Ormoc City to elucidate the secondary teachers' job satisfaction during the pandemic. Hence, this research gap motivates the survey study. In general, the article's main goal is to measure the level of job satisfaction of secondary school teachers and apply statistical inference to determine the influencing factors during distance education amid the pandemic. Specifically, the article sought the following attainable objectives: (1) to summarize the various socio-demographic profile of the secondary teachers; (2) to estimate the level of job satisfaction of the teachers in modular distance learning; (3) to elucidate the statistically significant factors of job satisfaction of teachers during the distance learning. The results of this research study may give helpful insights to secondary teachers in improving their well-being and professionalism despite the challenges and barriers in modular distance learning. Additionally, the findings might give some remedy for coping with stressful and depressing work as teachers that makes them satisfied with their teaching career. Furthermore, the study can be a baseline information for some policymakers in secondary education to improve teachers' benefits and privileges and can be a benchmark for some educational researchers and psychologists.

2. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

According to Bota (2013), job satisfaction is a subjective measure of a worker's fulfillment or contentedness with their assigned task in which they feel dedicated to work. Satisfaction of a teacher in their job is a vital component to perform better and ensure employee retention during the challenges of the COVID-19 pandemic. Apparently, the job satisfaction of teachers can be estimated in regard to affective, cognitive, and enthusiastic behavior they have experienced in the workplace (Burić & Moe, 2020). Kasalak and Dagyar (2020) emphasized that the job satisfaction of teachers refers to the enjoyment that derives and motivates them from their work and triggers their self-efficacy. However, during modular distance learning, teachers' job satisfaction is affected due to stress and exhaustion in their workload (Chitra, 2020; Chen et al., 2020; Islam et al., 2020). In the study of Nordin et al. (2020), it is stated that teachers' work satisfaction depends on the supervisor or school leader, as well as work assignments. Moreover, Dicke et al.

(2020) depicted that teachers' satisfaction in their job is affected by the student's academic performance and learning process. However, students' performance is adversely affected by the pandemic wherein their creativity and enjoyment in learning are relatively low (Casinillo, 2020). In that case, teachers' motivation to impart knowledge to their students amid the health crisis is negatively affected as well (Chitra, 2020). In fact, teachers are being burned out and depressed with their new nature of work in delivering their lessons which affects their well-being and satisfaction (Kumawat, 2020). Plus, teachers have encountered anxiety and emotional problems as they work because of uncertainty and health concerns with their loved ones (Auger & Formentin, 2021). In the paper of Singh and Bhattacharjee (2020), it is found that the job satisfaction of teachers is associated with their socio-demographic profile, education attainment, designation, benefits, and privileges in their service, among others. Thus, this research article dealt with a conceptual framework that aims to estimate the level of job satisfaction of secondary school teachers amid modular distance education. Furthermore, the study intends to capture the statistically significant predictors of job satisfaction among these teachers.

3. METHODOLOGY

Research Design

A descriptive-correlation research design was employed to give a description of variables of interest and determine the possible association between and among them. Cross-sectional data were gathered among secondary teachers in regard to job satisfaction and its causal determinants, and the data were summarized using some statistical measures. Plus, correlation analysis was calculated to capture the influencing factors of the teachers' job satisfaction during modular distance learning.

Participants, Sampling, and Ethics of the Study

The target participants of this study were the secondary teachers of Ormoc City, Leyte, Philippines who experienced modular distance learning during the pandemic. Three big high schools in the City of Ormoc were considered in this study such as Linao National High School (NHS), Margen NHS, and Valencia NHS. These three NHS were chosen for the reason that they have the highest rate of teacher turnover during the time of pandemic among the high schools in Ormoc City Division. In that case, it is a good indicator to study the job satisfaction of

teachers in the said schools. Using the formula below, the sample size was determined:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

The equation above is called Slovin's formula where *n* refers to the sample size of teachers, *N* pertains to the total number of teachers in the three chosen schools and *e* indicates the border of error which can be set by the researcher (Casinillo, 2019). So, the *e* in the formula was set to be 5% and the sample size is reasonable to extract a piece of representative information about the population characteristics. Plus, simple random sampling was used via random numbers so that every teacher in the population can have an equal chance to be selected as participants which eliminates the bias in the sampling procedure. Hence, Table 1 shows that in Margen NHS, 36 (67.92%) out of 53 teachers were drawn at random, in Linao NHS there were 44 (66.67%) out of 66 teachers, and in Valencia NHS there were 52 (65%) out of 80 teachers. Hence, a total of 132 (66.33%) out of 199 teachers were chosen as participants in this study.

Table 1. Fraction of Participants of the Study.

High Schools	N	n	%
Margen NHS	53	36	67.92
Linao NHS	66	44	66.67
Valencia NHS	80	52	65.00
Total	199	132	66.33

Before the study started, the researchers sought consent to formally and officially conduct the study. In that case, a formal letter was sent to the School Head of the Ormoc Division and principals of the chosen three high schools. Since the study was conducted during the lockdown of the pandemic, the researchers have completely observed the health protocols in the City of Ormoc. After the approval of the consent letters, the researchers directly informed the chosen participants and oriented them about the study. First, they were informed that their participation in the survey was voluntary and that all the information or data that will be gathered from them are solely used for this research article. Plus, they were informed that their responses are treated with confidentiality in view of the Data Privacy Act (Republic Act. 10173) of the country Philippines.

Research Questionnaire and Data Collection Procedure

As for the research instrument, the researchers developed a questionnaire that captures the job satisfaction of teachers adapted from the research paper of Ho et al. (2006) and Pazim (2021). The questionnaire consists of two sections. The first section was the socio-demographic and job profile of high school teachers such as age in years, sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, workplace (school assignment), number of years in service as a teacher, work status, job categorization, and net monthly income (Philippine Peso). In this section, the participants only checked the category that corresponds (closed-ended) to their answers. The following possible factors are selected based on the study by Singh and Bhattacharjee (2020), and Lau et al. (2022) which dealt with unaffected (socio-demographic profile) and affected (job profile) variables by the COVID-19 pandemic. According to their studies, the said factors were studied because they provide a sound argument to elucidate the teachers' job satisfaction during the pandemic. As for the second section, the researchers included 20 questions about job satisfaction which was aligned with modular distance learning. The 20-item questions follow a 5-point rating scale (Likert type) namely: 1 - Very dissatisfied, 2 - Dissatisfied, 3 - Neutral, 4 - Satisfied, 5 - Very satisfied. The questionnaire for job satisfaction has been evaluated by experts and found that it was valid in that it captures the well-being and motivation of teachers amid the pandemic. Additionally, the constructed questionnaire for job satisfaction was also reliable and possessed a Reliability score of 0.91 (Cronbach, 1951). The mean perception scores were calculated and Table 2 shows the different categories that it might fall.

Table 2. Teachers' job satisfaction score and its response.

Mean score	Response	Verbal description
1.00 - 1.80	Strong disagree	Very dissatisfied
1.81 - 2.60	Disagree	Dissatisfied
2.61 - 3.40	Neutral	Moderately satisfied
3.41 - 4.20	Agree	Satisfied
4.21 - 5.00	Strongly agree	Very satisfied

The questionnaire was personally given to the participants of the study and they were given enough time to respond. A participant who was not available at the time of the study or had missing data was replaced by an alternative participant drawn at random.

Data Analysis

After the data collection, the data were then encoded to Microsoft Excel aligned to the format of STATA statistical software. In order to give a description of the collected data, standard statistical measures (mean, standard deviation, frequency, and percentages) were calculated and presented in a table. Plus, in determining the factors of job satisfaction of high school teachers, the Chi-square test for association was employed by cross-tabulating the job satisfaction level and the different profiles of the teachers. Furthermore, the significant association among these variables was tested at the following likelihoods: 1%, 5%, and 10% levels.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

High School Teachers' Profile

Table 3 presents the socio-demographic and work profile of high school teachers in Ormoc City Division during modular distance learning using descriptive measures. Dominantly, there are 76.5% of the high school teachers are female and only 23.5% are male teachers. Most (44.7%) of these teachers are young (20-30 years old) which consists of almost half, about 27.3% of them are aged 31-40 years old, about 21.2% of them are aged 41-50 years old, and there are only 6.8% of them are in retirable age (51-65 years old). On average, the high school teachers' mean age is close to 34.7 years old. In that case, most of them are married teachers (62.9%) who have more responsibility at home compared to non-married teachers. There are 34.1% of these teachers are in a single stage of life, and only 1.5% of them are widowers and separated from their partners.

Only 1 (0.76%) of this group of teachers has finished a Doctorate degree in education about 28.8% of them have a Master's degree in education and dominant (70.5%) of them are just a graduate of bachelor's degree. About 33.3% of them are assigned to teach in Linao NHS, about 27.3% of them are in Margen NHS and 39.4% of them are in Valencia NHS. Dominant (42.4%) of these high teachers in Ormoc City are about 1-5 years in service as a teacher, 40.9% of them are about 6-10 years, about 6.8% of them are within 11-15 years, about 6.1% of them are about 16-20 years, about 2.3% of them are within 21-25 years, and lastly, about 1.5% of them are within 26-30 years in service as a professional teacher.

Approximately, the teachers' mean average number of years in service is close to 7.47. As for the work status, only 0.8% of them have a substitute status, wherein the teacher has to wait for an item classification or vacant position. There

are about 4.6% of these teachers have provisional status, and most (94.7%) of them has regular item position wherein they are already secured in tenurial position. In addition to that, most (92.4%) of these high school teachers are categorized as Teacher I-III, only 6.06% of them are categorized as Master Teacher I-II, and only 1.52% are Master Teacher III-IV. Furthermore, most (84.09%) of these high school teachers have a net monthly income of 21,000-30,000 (PHP), about 15.2% of them have 31,000-40,000 (PHP), and about 0.8% of them have a net income of 10,000-20,000 (PHP). On average, the mean net monthly income of these high school teachers is close to 26,935.6 (PHP).

Table 3. Frequency distribution for socio-demographic and work profile

Profile	Category	n	%
Sex	Male	31	23.5
	Female	101	76.5
Age (in years)	20-30 years old	59	44.7
	31-40 years old	36	27.3
	41-50 years old	28	21.2
	51-65 years old	9	6.8
	<i>Mean</i>		34.7
Civil Status	Single	45	34.1
	Married	83	62.9
	Widower	2	1.5
	Separated from partner	2	1.5
Highest Educational Attainment	Bachelors Degree	93	70.5
	Masters Degree	38	28.8
	Doctorate Degree	1	0.76
Workplace (High school assignment)	Linao NHS	44	33.3
	Margen NHS	36	27.3
	Valencia NHS	52	39.4
Number of Years in Service	1 - 5 years	56	42.4
	6 - 10 years	54	40.9
	11 - 15 years	9	6.8
	16 - 20 years	8	6.1
	21 - 25 years	3	2.3
	26 - 30 years	2	1.5
	<i>Mean</i>		7.47
Work Status	Substitute	1	0.8
	Provisional	6	4.6
	Regular Permanent	125	94.7
Job Categorization	Teacher I-III	122	92.4

	Master Teacher I-II	8	6.1
	Master Teacher III-IV	2	1.5
Net Monthly Income (PHP)	10,000-20,000	1	0.8
	21,000-30,000	111	84.1
	31,000-40,000	20	15.2
	<i>Mean</i>		26,935.6

Note: PHP - Philippine Peso (1 USD = 55.48 PHP); NHS - National High School

Job Satisfaction of High School Teachers

As shown in Table 4, there is no teacher who is very dissatisfied with their work during modular distance learning. Although their work is challenging exhausting, and sometimes risky, they still do their job as a professional teacher in public service. There are only a few (4.55%) of these teachers who are experiencing dissatisfaction with the job during modular distance learning (Table 4). These teachers are having a difficult time adjusting to the demands of work in the modular type of learning and experiencing stress and job burnout as they do their work assignments. In fact, Auger and Formentin (2021) depicted that during the pandemic, teachers are emotionally depressed by the amount of work and uncertainty of the pandemic. There are 35.61% of the high school teachers said that they are neutral in their job satisfaction and interpreted as moderately satisfied (Table 4). In that case, these teachers are somehow affected by the difficulties during the new normal but still working and doing their job as moderately satisfied in regard to their outputs. Chitra (2020) depicted that teachers' motivation is adversely affected by occupational stress during the pandemic period, hence, job satisfaction is somewhat affected and getting to a lower level. Most (56.82%) high school teachers are satisfied working during modular distance learning despite the difficulties and obstacles that they are facing as they impart knowledge to students. According to Li and Yu (2022), although teachers are being challenged by the unexpected situation in the pandemic, still teachers are working as a professional, and with a commitment they can change the lives of their students in regard to their education. In that case, they still work as they ignore the barriers and limitations in distance education and are still satisfied with their job assignment. In fact, about 3.03% of these teachers are very satisfied with their work assignments in modular distance learning. These teachers are not affected by the adverse impact of the pandemic but instead, they are very resilient and have a good level of self-efficacy that makes them motivated to work (Mullen et al., 2021). On average, Table 4 depicted that these teachers are satisfied ($M=3.49$, $SD=0.49$) with their job as professional educators during modular distance learning. This indicates that teachers are still working at their best to continue the educational

process despite the risk and uncertainty of the pandemic (Kasalak & Dagyar, 2020; Banal & Cruz, 2022).

Table 4. Job Satisfaction Level of high school teachers

Response	Frequency	Percentages (%)	Verbal description
Strongly disagree	0	0.00	Very dissatisfied
Disagree	6	4.55	Dissatisfied
Neutral	47	35.61	Moderately satisfied
Agree	75	56.82	Satisfied
Strongly agree	4	3.03	Very satisfied
Mean (\pm SD)		3.49 (\pm 0.49)	Satisfied ^a

Note: a - See Table 2

Determinants of Job Satisfaction of High School Teachers

Using the Chi-square test for association, Table 4 depicts the non-significant and significant determinants of job satisfaction of secondary school teachers during modular distance learning. In that case, it is found that the sex of teachers ($X^2=1.75$, p -value=0.63), age in years ($X^2=10.76$, p -value=0.29), and civil status ($X^2=5.66$, p -value=0.77), are not significant correlates of job satisfaction during the new normal setup in education. This indicates that those demographic profiles (sex, age, and civil status) do not contribute to the job satisfaction of teachers or the level of satisfaction in teaching does not vary on that profile. In addition, the following work profile does not influence the high school teachers' job satisfaction: years in service ($X^2=10.76$, p -value=0.29), work status ($X^2=10.76$, p -value=0.29), and net monthly income ($X^2=10.76$, p -value=0.29). This implies that the experience in teaching, being secured as a tenured faculty, and money do not contribute to their satisfaction level in doing their job as a teacher amid the pandemic.

Table 5 has shown that educational attainment ($X^2=39.35$, p -value<0.01) of high school teachers is significantly associated with their job satisfaction during modular distance learning at a 1% level. As presented in Table 6, it is found that most satisfied teachers have only a bachelor's degree as the highest educational attainment. Teachers of this type are relatively young and competitive in their jobs which do not focus on the barriers of distance learning but are more dedicated to their work assignments (Nguyen, 2020). Moreover, being young teachers, they are doing their job well so that they can be promoted to higher ranks which motivates them to be resilient despite difficulties during the new normal (Mullen et al., 2021).

Table 5. Causal determinants influencing the job satisfaction of high school teachers

Causal determinants	CHI-SQUARE TEST FOR ASSOCIATION		
	χ^2	<i>df</i>	<i>p-value</i>
Sex	1.75 ^{ns}	3	0.63
Age (in years)	10.76 ^{ns}	9	0.29
Civil Status	5.66 ^{ns}	9	0.77
Educational Attainment	39.35**	6	<0.01
Workplace (High school assignment)	36.52**	6	<0.01
Number of Years in Service	23.19 ^{ns}	18	0.18
Work Status	2.69 ^{ns}	6	0.85
Job Categorization	13.63*	6	0.03
Net Monthly Income	5.89 ^{ns}	6	0.44

Note: ns - not significant; ** - significant at 1%; * - significant at 5%.

Table 6. Cross-tabulation between highest educational attainment and job satisfaction

Educational Attainment	Job Satisfaction				Total
	Dissatisfied	Moderately satisfied	Satisfied	Very satisfied	
Bachelors Degree	2	37	53	1	93
Masters Degree	4	10	22	2	38
Doctorate Degree	0	0	0	1	1
Total	6	47	75	4	132

In addition, Table 5 presented that workplace or work-school assignment ($X^2=36.52$, $p\text{-value}<0.01$) is dependent on the job satisfaction of the high school teachers amid the pandemic at a 1% level of significance. This indicates that a conducive and healthy atmosphere does contribute to their motivation and satisfaction in work despite the challenges in modular distance learning. As shown in Table 7, teachers in Linao NHS are more satisfied in their job and teachers in Valencia NHS are mostly moderately satisfied. In the study of Erichsen and Reynolds (2020), it is mentioned that if the teachers have experienced a good atmosphere and morale in their workplace, they tend to do their job well. Additionally, Collie et al. (2020) found that if teachers are treated well in their workplace and provided suitable resources, they are likely motivated and satisfied as a worker despite the barriers in the pandemic. Furthermore, Taylor and Frechette (2022) mentioned that the teacher's productivity and well-being are

dependent on the workload assignment in respective schools wherein job satisfaction also varies.

Table 7. Cross-tabulation between workplace and job satisfaction

Workplace (High school assignment)	Job Satisfaction				Total
	Dissatisfied	Moderately satisfied	Satisfied	Very satisfied	
Linao NHS	2	10	32	0	44
Margen NHS	1	5	26	4	36
Valencia NHS	3	32	17	0	52
Total	6	47	75	4	132

On the other hand, Table 5 depicted that job categorization ($X^2=13.63$, p -value=0.03) is significantly correlated to the job satisfaction of high school teachers during the COVID-19 pandemic lockdown. This means that the job satisfaction level will vary depending on their job rank. It is worth noting that a higher rank has higher responsibility as opposed to a lower position. Hence, during the pandemic teachers with higher responsibilities are experiencing exhaustion in their job and being burnout. According to the study of Banal and Cruz (2022), workload assignment during distance learning matters which affects their resilience and well-being. Conversely, teachers with a lighter load during the pandemic result in higher job satisfaction and well-being compared to higher responsibilities (Lau et al., 2022).

Table 8. Cross-tabulation between job categorization and job satisfaction

Job categorization	Job Satisfaction				Total
	Dissatisfied	Moderately satisfied	Satisfied	Very satisfied	
Teacher I-III	5	44	70	3	122
Master Teacher I-II	0	2	5	1	8
Master Teacher III-IV	1	1	0	0	2
Total	6	47	75	4	132

5. CONCLUSION

The article aims to measure the job satisfaction of high school teachers and determine the factors affecting it during modular distance learning amid the lockdown of the pandemic. The findings showed that the secondary teachers during the modular distance education are satisfied in their jobs despite the

challenges they have encountered amid the COVID-19 pandemic. This means that even if they have encountered barriers and limitations in doing their job as an educator, they still work as professional teachers with dedication and resilience. In conclusion, teachers don't mind their fears and anxiety brought about by health crises but they still pursue their goals as teachers to impart suitable knowledge for their students. Moreover, the Chi-square test for independence has shown that if the highest educational attainment is a bachelor's degree, the workplace assignment is conducive and manageable, and lower job categorization are the determinants of work satisfaction among high school teachers during modular distance education. Conclusively, it implies that teachers with doable workloads are more satisfied in their jobs during the pandemic. In addition, if the teachers find their work comfortable and conducive, they are motivated and have high resilience levels to work despite the challenges and obstacles they have encountered during distance education. Hence, the study strongly recommends that school leaders or principals adjust the workload of teachers to avoid job burnout and exhaustion from work that gives them stress and depression. Plus, teachers must be provided with stress management or leisure time and give them privileges like day-offs or vacations to relieve from nerve-racking environments. As for further studies, one may include the opinion of students that might support the current results of this study to strengthen its argument about the job satisfaction level during the pandemic. In addition, aside from students' opinion, other possible factors may be obtained from the survey participants. These include class size, number of classes handled per day or week, time spent on admin tasks per day or per week, time spent on class proper, time spent to prepare for class, etc. This is to quantify workload and verify its impact on job satisfaction.

6. CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that no conflict of interest exists.

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